

education. If the new science and technology curriculum is to be successful in improving students' scientific literacy and interest in physics, this deficiency must be considered and overcome.

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APPLICATION OF ACTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Abdykerimova E.,

Aitbayeva L.

*candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor,
Caspian university of technology and engineering named after Sh.Yessenov,
Aktay, Kazakhstan*

Abstract

In the article the necessity of application of active learning methods and the influence of teaching methods on results of training of specialists in higher educational institutions. Choosing a method of teaching, the teacher takes into account the time allotted for the study of this topic, as well as the importance of educational material for further professional or educational activities of the student. But we must remember that learning is not only the assimilation of knowledge and skills, but also the development, education of students. The objectives of training in modern conditions is not so much the mastery of knowledge and skills in the chosen specialty as the preparation of students for self-education, the development of their interest in learning and the formation of cognitive needs. Recommendations for the implementation of active methods in the educational process were proposed. Active learning methods help to achieve the goals and contribute to personal and professional growth.

Keywords: active methods, interactive methods, training, computer science, didactic tasks.

The role of education in the current period of Kazakhstan's development is determined by the tasks and requirements of the rapidly developing modern society. Current trends in educational institutions are the reason for the training of highly qualified specialists of various profiles. Today, the main task is not to give students a certain knowledge, but to influence the way of thinking and the way of looking at the phenomena. Ensuring the quality training of specialists often depends on the effectiveness of the educational process. The future specialist needs not only to have deep and flexible professional knowledge and business skills, but also to have developed professional and social qualities and characteristics. In other words, the current level of development of production directs a modern specialist to the need to master professional skills at the level of professional competence. Professional competences allow to adapt to changing conditions in the labor market.

The use of active teaching methods in the teaching of computer science teaching methodology is based on a number of reasons: firstly, students should not only acquire certain knowledge, but should be able to apply it in a real practical situation.

Active learning is, first of all, new types, methods and tools of so-called active learning. Complex and purposeful use of technical tools is of great importance in improving educational processes, but the most important thing in the educational process is the

student's activity. Active methods include all kinds of classroom lessons with students.

During the lesson, the use of methods such as «Case Method», «Business games», «round table», etc. significantly activates the educational process. These methods contribute to the active interaction of students and teachers.

In order to improve and activate the educational process in higher educational institutions, it is of great importance to know and take into account the peculiarities of education, they create the need to reconstruct the stereotypes of educational work formed at school and arm them with new business and educational-cognitive activity skills.

Scientists and methodologists, teachers such as A. Alimov, F. B. Buribekova, N. zh. Zhanatbekova, A. K. Bekbolganova and others contribute to the development of active teaching methods.

In his works, A. Alimov not only substantiated the need for the use of active methods in all types of educational work of students, but also introduced the concept of problem-dialogical learning as a complete bearer of the essence of the processes of joint activity of teachers and students, as well as their mutual activity in the framework of «subject-subjective» relations.

The use of problem-based and developmental learning in practice has led to the emergence of so-called «active» methods. The formation of active

learning is one of the tools for the development of cognitive activity.

As a means of developing students' cognitive activity, active learning methods can be divided into three groups. These are programmed learning, problem learning, interactive (communicative) learning methods. In interactive methods, not only the student, but also the teacher can not only discuss scientifically proven points of view, but also express their own personal view of the problem, worldview and moral position.

Active teaching methods encourage students to think actively and do practical activities while learning the learning material. The main thing is not to memorize and retell the teacher's ready-made knowledge, but to use a system of methods aimed at students' independent acquisition of knowledge and business in the process of active thinking and practical action. Features of active methods of teaching are to stimulate thinking and action.

The emergence and development of active methods provides new tasks for teaching: not only education for students, but also formation and development of cognitive interests and abilities, creative thinking, skills of independent mental work and entrepreneurship. Active learning differs from traditional learning in a number of features, which, first of all, involves making students active by creating special conditions that promote activeness.

Active teaching is the organization and conduct of the educational process aimed at comprehensively revitalizing the educational and cognitive activity of students by using didactic and organizational-management tools as comprehensively as possible. Revitalization of education can proceed by improving the forms and methods of education and improving the organization and management of the educational process as a whole. They stimulate the cognitive activity of students and are mainly based on dialogue, which assumes a free exchange of ideas about ways to solve a problem. The possibilities of teaching methods in terms of improvement of educational activities are different, they depend on the nature and content of the relevant method, the methodology of their use, and the skill of the teacher.

The use of active teaching methods allows the teacher to create a positive microclimate in the group, which creates an atmosphere of free communication in the classroom. In addition, there was a need to create didactic conditions that would change the motivation of teaching for the better. The basis of the psychological theory of learning is the active cognitive activity of the student, which is formed with the help of the formation of creative thinking ability and professional competences acquired during the service. There are many active learning methods in pedagogy. One of them is the interactive method.

If we clarify the concept of interactive teaching methods, the word «Interactive» comes from the English word «interact». «Inter» means mutual, and «act» means action. Interactive - the ability to talk, dialogue, interact or communicate with students in a group. Interactive learning is dialogic learning in which

the teacher and student interact. The essence of interactive learning is that in the learning process, all students of the learning group are not only involved in the learning process, but also have the opportunity to understand what they know and think.

Interactive learning methods include: heuristic conversation, discussion method, brainstorming, round table method, business game method, case method, etc. Each of these methods not only has value, but also has its own characteristics. For example, a heuristic conversation is a shortened method of the learning method I find, open, search. By its psychological nature, heuristic conversation is accepted on the basis of collective thinking or conversation (when looking for an answer to a problem), in pedagogy, this method is considered a method of problem-based learning.

«Discussion» has been used as a teaching method in recent years. The discussion method is usually a specially programmed free discussion of the theoretical questions of the curriculum. In addition, it is used when students have to speak in group lessons, seminars, practical and laboratory lessons, in discussions on the results of tasks. Sometimes lecture-discussions are also used in practice, when the lecturer addresses the audience with personal questions that require a short and quick answer during the presentation of the material. The entire material of the lecture cannot be fully discussed in the debate, but the question that caused several different answers from the audience forms the psychological climate of collective thought and readiness to listen carefully to the opinion of the lecturer who answers the debate question, taking into account the existing situation.

«Round table» method is organized to discuss any issue. In education, the «round table» method is mainly considered in order to increase the efficiency of mastering theoretical problems in various scientific aspects, with the participation of specialists of various backgrounds.

The «business game» method is used in research work, in the process of project development, and in the development of collective solutions. Business games are often used to teach management activities in the training of specialists of various profiles in higher educational institutions. The business game method as a teaching method is the task of teaching students not in real objects, but in models, in order to train future professionals to perform relevant professional functions.

The basis of the «Project» method is the development of students' cognitive skills, the ability to independently compile their knowledge, the ability to navigate in the information space, and the development of critical thinking. The method of projects, on the one hand, suggests the use of various methods, teaching tools, and on the other hand, the integration of knowledge and business from various fields of science. The theoretical result of the project is the presentation of solutions to the researched problem, and the practical result is a real project ready for implementation. This method allows to form research skills and develop development projects. For example, prepare a project

on the topic «My future profession» and defend it with a presentation made in Microsoft Power Point.

"Brainstorming" method is widely used as a teaching method in higher educational institutions. The purpose of this method is to organize a collective thinking activity in search of non-traditional ways to solve problems. It is the search for an answer to any complex problem through the intense statement and opinions of the expressed ideas, predictions, thoughts and suggestions. In addition, the golden rule of brainstorming is that the opinions expressed by the conversation participants should not be questioned or criticized, but should provide complete freedom of any ideas. This method forms the skills of concentrating attention, thinking efforts in solving a specific problem, as well as forming the experience of collective thinking activities and the ability to work in a small group. As an example, brainstorming questions on the topic «Information Retrieval and Protection» are displayed on the board:

1. What should be done with the information so that it is easy to find the necessary information?

2. In what ways can information be protected from unauthorized access?

2 sheets are given for each group's ideas (information search, information protection). The brainstorming begins. The teacher comes to each group in turn and provides the necessary assistance. After the time has passed, the timeout will be announced.

The second stage of brainstorming is the analysis of ideas. Each group looks at their ideas, corrects the conclusions and puts them on the board with magnets. We compare the number of expressed ideas and try to evaluate them. For the most ideas, a token is awarded for a unique proposal.

The third stage is processing the results. It can be spent in the form of book work. Go through the textbook quickly and match the group's suggestions with the sentences in the text. If it matches the textbook - 1 token is given, if there is a new interesting idea - 2 tokens. Then he writes down the topic of the lesson, the found ways of searching for information and protecting it in a notebook.

«Browse Gallery» method. In this method, groups (two, three) are given topics. He defends his thoughts on this topic on a poster.

Purpose: groups to defend their work, ideas, present unique ideas based on the prepared poster. The effectiveness of this method is to evaluate and collect the student's thoughts. He knows the opinion of others on the topic, discusses his thoughts with students in the group, expands his knowledge and understanding by making an expert opinion on the topic.

The «picture speaks» method. This method is to tell your opinion by looking at different pictures. For example, you can simply show pictures of people, such as Thomas Knoll and John Knoll, without providing any explanatory material, use the Internet, and ask students to write down who they are, what they did, and sequence their answers.

«Venn diagram» method. Using this method, for example, you can be asked to find commonalities of types of graphic editors and the editor's features,

advantages and disadvantages, where students critically reflect on the points they read in lecture materials, Internet resources, write and defend in a diagram. The second group listens and adds to this idea by listening and completes the idea. This encourages students to be inquisitive.

The Six Hats of Mind is a method developed by Edward de Bono, which is a parallel thinking process that allows you to focus your thoughts on one problem from among different solutions. For example, the subject: «Internet». White hat - focusing on the necessary information or facts (for example, through facts about the Internet, provides information). Yellow hat - logical positive thinking, that is, studying the positive aspects of an idea, looking for its successes and advantages (for example, we can get documents and information through the Internet at any time, make utility payments, monitor our children's lessons, get in line for kindergarten, get address information etc.). Red hat - expressing inner feelings, predictions and intuition (for example, finding a friend after several years on the Internet and expressing joy). Black hat - thinking of the logical negative, assessing the wrong side (for example, sitting a lot on the Internet, it is harmful to the eyes, the demand for books decreases, it leads to family breakdown, etc.). Green hat is creative thinking, i.e., new thinking that creates alternative, new ideas (for example, if there was an electronic version of the student's book on the Internet, so that the student could study each subject, then the students would not carry a heavy bag full of books; a student's notebook it is checked with a scanner according to a certain criterion, and if the answer is in front of the teacher the next day, comments are made, and it leads students to creativity). The blue hat is thought process management. It is a monitoring mechanism that ensures that the requirements of all six hats are being properly met, providing expertise to each group.

«Language is an art» method. In this method, a hidden word is read to students in a mysterious way. Students who find the left word and say it in Kazakh, Russian, and English will be awarded points. For example,

1. Information about the environment and the processes taking place there (information);

2. Source of information (nature);

What data does the phonograph program process (sound);

Deficiency in the program or text (mistake, error, error);

An additional device that facilitates working with a computer (mouse).

The "Seven Riddles" method. In this method, a mystery is hidden for the learners. The student who solves the riddle gets a point.

1. Information on paper

Enters into computer (scanner)

2. You don't have to worry if you press the trigger
Writes paper without pen (keyboard)

3. Its location on the surface of the screen
Always flashing (cursor)

4. I live at the computer

I am a cure for it (anti-virus program)

5. Uzuntura Zhalkaubek

He always lies down without getting up

Follow him if he moves

No character left (space)

«Live» method. Students in a group form a circle. In the middle of the circle, the "reporter" asks various questions to the students who came to the live broadcast. Students answer.

Here, your opinion on this question?

Who wants to add to this comment?

What is your opinion on this question?

What do you say? You can ask questions in this direction. The cameraman is filming the live broadcast from outside. Then it displays this video file on the interactive panel. The teacher summarizes and sums up this live broadcast, tells who gave the best ideas, and concludes.

"Open mic» method. Purpose: To train the student to think quickly and clearly. Students hold a microphone in their hands and ask questions related to past lessons or homework, and the second student answers.

«Kinometaphor» method. Knowing the student's own thoughts and opinions by showing a clip from a video on one issue. Purpose: to develop the student's mindset and thinking ability.

In the lesson, you can also use the method «Put in the missing words or find their place». In this method, for example, you can write down the function of the menu commands and ask to fill in the missing words while reading it. That is, ordering to write the name of the team in three languages. And in the opposite direction. For example, in the following example: ____ is a command to change the brightness, saturation and color of individual color viewers of the video, this can be done using the ____ keyboard shortcut. (empty, unwritten command name Hue/Saturation, Color / Saturation, Color / Saturation; keyboard shortcut Ctrl+U).

"Thinking" method. The "Thinking" method should be composed of sentences by placing the words in the correct order from the small pieces of paper that contain the words of the sentences that form the main concepts and definitions of the topic. Effectiveness of this method: logical thinking of students develops, quick thinking.

"Jigsaw" method. Groups are assigned to read a text on individual topics. Each student reads individually (5 minutes). Students in groups tell each other and discuss in groups (5 minutes). One student from each group goes to other groups and explains their text. In this way, the materials read by each group are exchanged. Effectiveness: pronunciation, listening, saves time, group work. Here all students come into contact.

The most effective and widespread method of organizing students' active cognitive activity is the «case method». The method of analyzing real situations develops the ability to analyze life tasks. When faced with a real situation, the learner must determine whether there is a problem, what it consists of, and his attitude to the situation. The peculiarity of this method is that the teacher does not give a qualitative assessment and any opinion is accepted as permissible. Let's look at an example.

The subject. Graphic editor. Drawing in a graphic editor

Purpose: to contribute to the acquisition and systematization of knowledge about the graphic editor; improving the skills of working with graphic editor tools; development of a creative personality; formation of personal responsibility for the result.

Description of the situation: Now you are artists. Your task is to depict how you imagine your homeland. Watch a video about Kazakhstan (at the teacher's discretion). I hope this video fragment will help you choose the success of the future plot.

Case problem: How do you imagine your homeland? Visualize it using the tools of the graphic editor.

The subject. Charting in MS Excel spreadsheet

Purpose: to systematize knowledge, enter data into electronic tables; improving the ability to work with functions; formation of skills to select and create diagrams based on given data; development of problem solving skills.

Situation description: Your task was to measure and record the air temperature for a week. So, you need to act as a meteorologist and use a spreadsheet program to create a table with the temperature regimes you have specified. Based on table information, create a chart, determine the warmest day, coldest day and average temperature of the week.

Case question: What functions are used to find maximum or minimum values? How can I make a graph for these numerical values? Does each diagram show the temperature regime of the air?

Role playing method.

Subject: Information technology court.

The purpose of the lesson: to develop the ability to work in a group and to work independently with literature.

Purpose: to check that students understand the purpose and functions of ICT; assessment of what types of information processes are familiar; assessment of the role of information and ICT in the development of modern society.

For this game, the group of students will be divided into «accusers», «defenders» and «members of the court» led by the chairman of the court, and the rest of the students will be «spectators» in the courtroom.

At the beginning of the lesson, the rules of behavior in the «court» and description of roles are distributed to students. The accusers must formulate what kind of harm ICT has in front of humanity. Advocates, accordingly, must select arguments in favor of ICTs for human development. The court must make a conclusion whether the active penetration of ICT into all spheres of human activity or vice versa contributes to the harmonious development of society. The court is given 15 minutes to prepare. At the same time, it is allowed to use pre-selected literature.

The main challenge in conducting lessons using active learning methods is to engage students according to their specific learning style. In this case, the roles should be properly divided.

When using active methods, the effectiveness in learning the learning material is evaluated differently. For example, if the learning of information in the

lecture form of studying the material does not exceed 20%, in the business game - up to 90%. Experimental data of H. E. Meichner confirm the superiority of interactive methods in the educational process. He said that learners remember 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see, 50% of what they hear and see, and when they actively receive information, they remember 80% of what they say, and 90% of what they do.

Interactive activity in the classroom involves the organization and development of dialogic communication, which leads not only to mutual understanding and interaction, but also to the joint solution of common and important tasks for each participant. During dialogic learning, students learn not only critical thinking, situation analysis and solving complex problems based on relevant information, but also weigh alternative opinions, make thoughtful decisions, participate in discussions and communicate with other people. When using interactive methods, when students search for truth collectively, the observed competition has a great impact on intellectual activity.

During the development of scientific and technical progress, the amount of information necessary for mastering is increasing. Information quickly becomes outdated and needs constant updating. In this regard, training aimed at memorizing the material in memory and retaining the learned material can meet modern requirements. This is the problem of forming the qualities of thinking that allow the student to learn a constant stream of new information on his own, to

develop abilities that will be preserved after the completion of education and ensure the ability of a person to stay abreast of the accelerated scientific and technical progress. There is a need for new methods and methods of teaching that teach students to learn, that is, to find and learn the necessary information independently. The teacher's role is to draw conclusions about the student's work and to point out mistakes during the execution of tasks.

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THE ROLE AND PLACE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE CURRENT EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

**Abdykerimova E.,
Aitbayeva L.**

*Caspian university of technology and engineering named after Sh.Yessenov,
Aktay, Kazakhstan*

Abstract

The article discusses interactive methods and the significance of their role and place in the modern educational process, the features of their application, the general results and effects of interactive learning. The necessity of using interactive teaching methods is considered, emphasizing their important role in improving the quality of education. There will be kinds of active learning methods. Modern teaching methods are noted and a brief summary of their content is given. The experimentally revealed features of the attitude of high school students to the activity of perception and interpretation of the author's text and writing an essay based on what they have read are described, the reasons for their difficulties are identified. Features of interactive methods, their advantages, the activities of the teacher and student in the context of interactive learning. Ways to improve the efficiency of the process of working on text activities in high school are described and numerous examples of interactive exercises and tasks for students are given, which can be used both in computer science lessons and as part of elective courses, in extracurricular activities. The article includes the development of role-playing games, cases, quest.

Keywords: interactive teaching methods, role-playing games, demonstration, work in small groups, discussion, technique, training, interactive, practice, innovation.

The growth of spiritual and material needs of society creates the need to increase the level of social maturity of society members, their readiness for dialogue and self-knowledge. In this regard, the current educational process cannot be based on an educational approach. Today, everyone knows the importance of

teaching schoolchildren to think, understand, and act. Therefore, interactive learning methods, i.e. «methods of purposeful enhanced intersubjective interaction between the teacher and students to create optimal conditions for their development» are of particular relevance. Interactive methods, in particular, group discussion,